

The Fabry-Perot Interferometer Manual

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1 The Fabry-Perot Interferometer

The Fabry-Perot Interferometer (diagram represented in Figure 1), FPI for now on, is a high resolution interferometer that makes use of multiple reflections of the light combined with an objective lens that creates an interference pattern that is the convolution of the source airglow Gaussian function (representing the velocity distribution that is being observed) with the FPI instrument function. The etalon is an *etalon* optical component consisting of two partially reflective mirrors that combines with the objective lens to create a multi-beam interference pattern.

The purpose of this manual is to walk you through the various steps of the FPI assembly and operation, and it should cover most of the issues relative to it. In case of any questions, do not hesitate in contact us:

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Figure 1: Cut diagram of the FPI system in the calibration mode - SkyScanner looking down to the scattering chamber.

2 Main parts of the FPI

As we see in Figure 1, the FPI is not a *single-piece* kind of equipment. It consists of an assembly of sub-parts that taken together (details described in the next section) makes up the FPI instrument.

The following list of figures shows the **main** parts of our equipment - attached to this document you should find a detailed shipping list.

(a) Etalon

(b) Sky scanner

Figure 2: Main parts of the FPI

(c) HeNe frequency stabilized laser

(d) Advantech Computer

(e) CCD camera

(f) Interference filter

(g) Objective lens

(h) Sky scanner's cables

Figure 2: Main parts of the FPI

3 Assembly

Before we start with the ring centering procedure, we discuss the integration of the key components of the FPI. Use extreme caution while doing all of the following steps, specially when the instruction tells you to handle the **etalon** (Figure 2a), the **camera** (Figure 2e), and the **filter** (Figure 2f) or whenever the instruction is marked with the symbol \triangle .

1. Make sure that all the parts are clean, specially the optics parts, such as the mirrors, the lens, the filter and their respective trays;
 - (a) Do so very carefully by using proper lens cleaning cloths available in the lens cleaning kit;
 - (b) Dry the excess of alcohol and any other residues from the optics with microfiber cloth. **Failing to do so will result in scratches in the surface of the optics.**; \triangle
2. Place the FPI stand on top of the building;
3. Install the Sky-Scanner (Figure 2b) with the retaining ring;
 - (a) Use the **8** bolts and ratcheted wrench;
4. Install the pre-calibrated frame from underneath using a boat wrench;
5. Then install the camera in the pre-calibrated frame, being careful to not change the adjustments screws;
6. Insert the lens into the lens cavity; \triangle
7. Install the etalon onto the etalon plate then place the etalon very carefully in a way that the holes in the frame match the holes in the etalon plate; \triangle
8. Install the light shield that covers the etalon;
9. Install the filter into the filter tray (or the filter wheel); make sure that the red side of the filter is down (to minimize ghost reflections) and the square retaining filter piece is facing toward the sky scanner.
10. Place the upper shield, aligning with the retaining ring, previously used to install the sky scanner, then slide the filter tray in place;
11. Finally adjust vertically the light shields in order to prevent any light contamination to come into the optical path.

4 Rings pattern focusing and centering procedure

As mentioned before, the frame is previously calibrated, in a controlled environment, to facilitate the deployment and its installation at the site. However, the shipping handling and the assembly process may cause the focus

become slightly out from the original calibrated position so that the laser image is no longer as sharp as before. To fix that, the user must follow the ring pattern focusing and centering procedure.

In order to do that the user must utilize the Andor SOLIS software (Figure 3e) (should be pre-loaded on the computer, but available in the NATION Dropbox). Make sure that the following parameters are met:

- In the bottom left corner, the program should show the word “OFF”. Double click it to open the temperature cooling control. After checking the “ON”, setup the temperature to be -80 degrees Celsius. You will notice that after clicking OK the CCD will start to cool down (*in case of disconnected camera the bottom left corner will show “101”*);
- The option FULLY AUTO must be checked in “/Hardware/Shutter Control”. That makes the built-in camera shutter to be controlled by the exposition;
- Go to “Setup Acquisition” and in exposure time enter 10 (value in seconds; may change depending on the circumstances). This step must be revisited every trial, since the intended signal is supposed to be less than 10 thousand counts per second - achieved by attenuating the laser lights - and peaks with less than 60 thousand counts - achieved by decreasing the exposure time);
- Check the 1024x1024 and 2x2 binning in the next one subsection over.

After hitting ”OK”, wait until the temperature of the CCD chip stabilizes (which is indicated in the bottom left corner, when the temperature screen becomes blue). If that is not the case, make sure that the camera is properly connected to the functional power supply, close Andor SOLIS and redo all these steps.

Once the temperature is stabilized and the acquisition is setup, you can go to the next step of ring focusing. That means to bring the camera to focal length of the lens and having all the other optical components perpendicular to the optical path.

The program Analyze has a feature of annular integration which produces a plot with greater ratio of signal to noise than the cross-section plots produced by Solis. So, a good practice at the conclusion of the focusing process is to run Master and Analyze in a continual exposure sequence separated by a few seconds (or use the PAUSE button in Master) to observe the peak heights of the outer rings. A sharper focus is one with higher peak heights and more narrow widths.

4.1 Ring focusing

The ring focusing process consists in bringing the whole equipment adjusted so the ring pattern focus exactly on the center of the CCD chip. This requires a series of very small adjustments in order to sharpen and center the rings and uniformly illuminate the CCD. This uniformity is critical to the successful analysis of the data.

At every step of the way you must take an exposure and redo the step. The idea is to make the image to look sharper, uniform, and centered; and do that by repeating each of these steps, improving the image up until the point it gets worse and move back to the “sweet spot”. You will take an image by pressing F5 on your keyboard or clicking on the clear green icon in the SOLIS program (have your monitor OFF, press the button and wait hear two clicks - opening and closing of the CCD’s shutter - while the exposure takes place).

Notice that each one of these steps corresponds to one kind of adjustment (highlighted in the text) to the image and once you are done with one step does not necessarily mean that you are finished with that particular step. The process is described as followed:

1. Turn on the laser (Figure 2c) and use the `Observatory.exe` (details described in the Section 5.1.2) to point the sky scanner (Figure 2b) to the calibration chamber;
2. Make sure that the FPI building is dark and all the LED lights are properly covered with black electrical tape or black cloth. The light contamination inside the room will contribute with eventual **non-uniformity**, by increasing the background on one side of the image relative to the other. Make sure that you carry charged flashlights for the following phases of this process;
3. Remove the filter tray with the filter from the frame. The presence of the filter will decrease a lot the amount of light that will go through the etalon, making your exposure time to be as long as 200 seconds. Without the filter you will bring the exposure time down to 5-20 seconds;
4. Mount the top of the camera at roughly 30 cm away from the lens in a leveled manner, using the 8 side screws. This is due to the fact that the focal length of the lens is 310 mm, but the CCD’s chip is roughly 1.7 cm deep into the top of the shutter and be sure that the camera is leveled by using a bubble level, this will make it more likely that the x-y adjustments will run smoothly with less stress in the camera’s plate. Use the z direction adjustment to help you with the camera’s placement and leveling. This step will most likely **improve the sharpness of the image**, meaning that the outer rings will be thin, but distinguishable from the background;
5. Tilt the etalon with the tilt screws in order to compensate for the wedge angle. The etalon is designed to have both plates parallel to each other, but not parallel to the top glass. You want to make sure that the etalon’s plates are perpendicular to the optical path. By doing that you will change the **placement of the rings** and the **uniformity of the image**. The uniformity of the rings should considerably improve. After you were done with this part, secure the tilt angles using the downward screws. Make sure to take an exposure before going to the next step, since many times after tilting the etalon will be only touching the frame in two points, making it unbalanced;

6. **Center the image** by using the x-y adjustment thumbscrews. You can easily rotate the thumbscrews if the top plate of the camera is leveled;

After going through this process, and repeating steps 3 through 5 you must have reached a sharp and somewhat uniform image at the center of the CCD field of view. In case you come up with a still non-uniform image (with a difference of under 10 counts from the dark to the bright side) (the sharpness of the image must be the same throughout the whole image as well), you have to fine adjust the camera in place. It always helps to compare the corners of the image (top and bottom/left and right).

At this point you want to use the z direction adjustment screws separately. Pick a screw, make a quarter turn and take an exposure. See if there is any improvement and repeat this step with a different screw, assessing the image every try until the image is perfectly sharp and uniform. Assess at every step of the way the change you just made. To achieve perfection in the ring sharpness, you have to eventually decrease the amount you turn in each screw. Not all the necessary changes will be one quarter turn, meaning that eventually you will start working with eighths and sixteenths of turns.

A great way to do the final adjustments in the laser ring pattern, is to run the `testLaserStability.txt` script in the FPI programs. In the next section we will discuss all the details on how to do so, and how to work with the programs necessary to get the test script going as well as the data taking process.

5 A3O programs and script language

5.1 A3O programs

As mentioned before, the FPI system is controlled by the Advantech computer (2d). It comes fully loaded with all the programs necessary to control the system, however, if in any case, you do not find the program we make reference to in this manual, please do not hesitate in contacting us. It is also worth it to mention that there is a help file called `A3O.htm`. It is certainly a good exercise to take a look at a file before you go on with the FPI operations.

Possibly the most important folder in the Advantech computer is the `C:\FPI_Programs\`. Inside that folder you will find, among other files, the `A3O.htm` and the following programs:

Figure 3: Main programs relative to the FPI control. (a) `Master.exe`, (b) `Observatory.exe`, (c) `Camera.exe`, (d) `Analyze.exe`, (e) `Andor Solis.exe`.

Inside that folder you will also find the file `PgmDefault.txt`, which is the program responsible to set the routine the `Master.exe` program will follow.

Figure 4: Master v1.06

Another important folder is `C:\KEO_Scripts\`. This represents a collection of all the text files (`.txt`) responsible for controlling the Figure 3a through 3d programs, and by consequence the data taking process. As mentioned before, the Andor Solis program is merely an easy access tool to setup an image acquisition and take images using the CCD camera. It can also be used to cool the CCD and/or open and close the CCD camera shutter.

5.1.1 Master

This represents the “head” of the FPI programs. The `Master.exe` (Figure 4) program will control the script chosen to run and manage the operations with `Observatory.exe`, `Camera.exe`, `Analyze.exe`. Figure 4 represents how the Master program looks with no operations running.

In case you were about to run some routine with master, you must open all the other FPI programs. If you happen to open one of the programs before Master, you will be running on the “stand-alone” mode (message in Figure 5 will pop-up), which basically means that you still have control over that particular program, but that program will not communicate with the others.

5.1.2 Observatory

The `Master.exe` relates to the control of the various pieces of hardware of the FPI. This program will communicate with **sky-scanner**, **laser USB shutter**, **filter wheel**¹. This is the program needed to move the sky-scanner to an intended position, therefore the one you will need to point the sky-scanner to the calibration chamber position described in Section 4.1.

¹When applicable.

Figure 5: Stand-alone message for the Observatory program

Figure 6: Observatory v1.63

Figure 8: Analyze v2.03 in stand-alone mode

```

AnalyzeControlFile.txt - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
// Analyze Control File version 1.85 Analyze

// QL parameters
write1D TRUE //output 1D interferogram into QL file
nAnnuli 500 // # annuli to use for integration 2-D image to 1-D interferogram
nPeaksExpected 2 // # peaks to be used in the 1-D interferogram (0=unknown how many peaks)

// QL ring center parameters
imageCtrPXX 1. // center of 630 image, units of pixels ->chip width of 256 taken as -128,128
imageCtrPXY -1.

centerUsing FILE

peakRange[0] 35, 65 // expected start/end position of 630 nm in pixels for peak 0
peakRange[1] 75, 120 // expected start/end position of 630 nm in pixels for peak 1

peakRangeLaser[0] 55,85 // where to look for the peaks in the laser image
peakRangeLaser[1] 100, 140

// Image processing table - determines how images are treated in real time
Process B annularIntegrate
Process K darkStore annularIntegrate
Process D darkStore annularIntegrate

Process L darkSubtract annularIntegrate peakLocate laserProcess

```

Figure 9: AnalyzeControlFile.txt

Figure 10: Fixed center position

Then finally reopen Analyze and look at the laser image one more time (you will have to reopen the image as well). The image now should look like what it is displayed in Figure 10. Notice that this time, the center of the image is correct, since the annular integration displays sharp Gaussian peaks as expected.

Figure 11 represents a good quality sky image from Poker/Alaska. Notice the broadening of the rings shown in both 2D image and 1D annular integration.

5.2 Script language

As you know by now, the FPI is operated by a series of programs (`Master.exe`, `Observatory.exe`, `Camera.exe` and `Analyze.exe`) running steps of a script. The scripts we will use are written by Mr. Devin J Wyatt, based on previous work by Dr. Meriwether and Dr. Makela (from UIUC). Mr Wyatt made major improvements in regard to the organization of the script language, making the interface rather friendly to the user.

The following list represents a series of steps that the system (ran by `Master.exe`) has to go through. Displayed here is the `laserTestStability.txt` script and it serves as an example of the script language operation.

1. As soon as you have all the four programs opened, starting with `Master.exe`, and you hit the button “Run” (see Figure 4), `Master.exe` will look for the file `PgmDefault.txt`.

Figure 11: Good quality sky image

```
// PgmDefault.txt
// This is the program that is run by Master
// Use OVERLAY to insert your own script to be run
//
// Master script
//
//OVERLAY 'Scripts\\Keo_PgmDefault'
//
OVERLAY 'Scripts\\Testing\\testLaserStability'
```

Box 1: PgmDefault.txt.

OVERLAY signals the script that will be run by Master. In between quotes the address of the script in the FPI computer. For the sake of the explanation, if you were to run the script in the path

C:\Scripts\Testing\testCamera.txt,

you must comment the whole file out using ‘//’ and type

```
OVERLAY 'Scripts\\Testing\\testCamera',
```

save the file and repeat first step.

- As you can see from Box 1, our `testLaserStability.txt` is selected to operate. This script will make the FPI to take a series of laser images, in prefixed intervals, to provide the user with the information needed to adjust the system to achieve a sharp ring pattern described in Section 4.1 and displayed in Figure 10. The user must provide the following information before hit Run on Master for the first time

```
// **** USER MODIFIABLE SETTINGS **** //
// Root directory for all data storage
dirDataRoot = 'C:\\FPIData\\'
// Root directory for FPI programs
dirProgramRoot = 'C:\\FPI_Programs\\'
// Unique site identifier
siteID = "ETH"
// CCD temperature
DesiredCCDTemp = -70.
// Sky-scanner position of the laser chamber
az_laser = 80.7
ze_laser = -175.6
// delay between cycles in seconds
cycleDelay = 300
// number of acquisitions
numTotalCycles = 165
```

Box 2: Commented testLaserStability.txt script.

For the ring focusing process the user is advised to use `cycleDelay = 30` seconds, and if any adjustments are needed, the user can always press “Pause” on Master, do the adjustments, and hit “Run” once again.

3. After getting the user modifiable settings Master will go on with the program. The program will setup a folder according to the day of the measurements. This folder will have the YYYYMMDD standard. Say if today is March 20th 2015, the program will create a folder named “dirProgramRoot/20150320”.
4. The program will then create the log files for each of the FPI programs. This will guarantee you all the information needed to debug the system. **In case of a possible issue, you must send the log files corresponding to the time when the problem took place when contacting us.**
5. Now the program will initialize a series of subroutines. These routines should be already setup and the user should not have to input in these. They are

```

// Initialize data types
CALL 'C:\\Scripts\\Utilities\\Keo_InitDataTypes'
// Initialize image sequence counters
CALL 'C:\\Scripts\\Utilities\\Keo_InitImageSequences'
// Initialize hardware types
CALL 'C:\\Scripts\\Utilities\\Keo_InitHardwareTypes'
// Initialize hardware configuration
CALL 'C:\\Scripts\\Configuration\\Keo_SetupHardware'
// Load exposure times
CALL 'C:\\Scripts\\Configuration\\Keo_SetupExposureTimes'
// Load the cycle acquisitions
// This populates numCycleAcquisitions and the az_pos and ze_pos
//arrays
CALL 'C:\\Scripts\\Configuration\\Keo_SetupCycleAcquisitionLaserCal'

```

Box 3: Commented CALL function of subroutines.

6. Then the program will start the CCD cooling until the temperature matches the `DesiredCCDTemp` variable inputted by the user (see Box 2).
7. Finally the program will take `numTotalCycle` measurements with a delay of `cycleDelay` seconds in between acquisitions.

The same procedure is repeated when doing normal sky measurements. The difference is that the program will calculate the position of the Sun and the Moon relative to the site and setup times for the measurements to take place. It will also take move the sky-scanner to the cardinal positions. **To setup for normal measurements, the user must OVERLAY “Keo_PgmDefault”.**

The KEO scripts, organized by Mr. Wyatt, allows the user to easily find a subroutine if needed. The structure of is as follow:

```

C:\FPIPrograms\Scripts\
    Configuration
        Keo_SetupCycleAcquisition.txt
        Keo_SetupExposureTimes.txt
        Keo_SetupPostCycleAcquisition.txt
        Keo_SetupPreCycleAcquisition.txt
        Keo_SetupSunEphemeris.txt
    Testing\
        Keo_RingCentering.txt
        testCamera.txt
        testObservatory.txt
        testUSBShutter.txt
    Utilities\

```

Keo_AcquireStoreDisplayImage.txt
Keo_DataType2ExpTime.txt
Keo_DataType2String.txt
Keo_IncrementImageSequence.txt
Keo_InitDataTypes.txt
Keo_InitImageSequences.txt
Keo_MoonAngle.txt
Keo_SunEphemerisTimes.txt
Keo_WaitSkyScanComplete.txt
Keo_ZenithTimeSearch.txt
Keo_PgmDefault.txt

5.2.1 KEO_SetupCycleAcquisition.txt

This is possibly one of the most important subroutines related to the KEO scripts. It is a configuration file that contains the sequence of positions that will the Master program will loop through.

This file brings four different pieces of information to each position

- `az_pos(i)`: Azimuth position of the sky-scanner ($0 < \text{az_pos}(i) < 360$)
- `ze_pos(i)`: Zenith position of the sky-scanner ($0 < \text{ze_pos}(i) < 180$)
- `data_type(i)`: Correspondent datatype of the measurement as
 - `dataTypeX`: Sky image;
 - `dataTypeD`: Sky dark image;
 - `dataTypeL`: Laser image;
 - `dataTypeK`: Laser dark image;
 - `dataTypeB`: Bias image;
- `analyze_tag(i)`: See `C:\FPIPrograms\AnalyzeControlFile.txt` for valid options.

5.2.2 KEO_SetupHardware.txt

Finally the subroutine that indicates the type of hardware you are using. There are two variables in this subroutine:

- `fwType`: Indicate whether or not the system has a filter wheel (device responsible to change filters for different wavelength measurements supposedly placed where the filter holder is, above the Etalon 1)
 - “FW_BU” for filter wheel;
 - “FW_NONE” for filter holder (single filter);
- `ccdType`: Indicate what CCD camera the FPI system is currently using.
 - “CCD_PIXIS” for Princeton cameras;
 - “CCD_IKON” for ANDOR cameras;